

Research Article

SORTIFY: The First Step to a Greener World

Mohamad Azfar Safwan Bin Lamin¹, Mohamad Syahmi Irfan Bin Johari², Iman Amadi Bin Abdul Hadi Andrew³, Nuratiqah Shazwani Binti Zawawi⁴, Hani Miasara Binti Hanipah⁵, Farah Kautsar Binti Kamal Basya⁶, Nazmi Harith-Fadzilah⁷ and Zulakmal Bin Abd. Manas⁸

¹ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak

² Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak

³ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak

⁴ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak

⁵ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak

⁶ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak; farahkautsar@mara.gov.my;

 ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6974-3513>)

⁷ The Microbiome Lab (TML), Universiti Malaysia Pahang Al-Sultan Abdullah, Lebuhr Persiaran Tun Khalil Yaakob, 26300, Gambang, Pahang, Malaysia; nazmiharith@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2472-1630>)

⁸ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak; zulakmal.manas@mara.gov.my

* Correspondence: farahkautsar@mara.gov.my; zulakmal.manas@mara.gov.my

Abstract: *The waste management problems have been a very prevalent issues globally, particularly among the developing countries. One significant problem in waste management is to efficiently carry out the waste sorting. The AI-based waste sorting system addresses rising plastic and metal waste by automating the sorting process using a robotic arm and conveyor integrated with the YOLO AI object detection model. It classified materials with high accuracy (88%–97%) and directed them into appropriate bins at within short period of time, supporting United Nations' Sustainability Development Goals 9 and 11. The system is scalable and suitable for factories. Operating at Technology Readiness Level 6, it offers real-time monitoring, enabling smarter, more sustainable waste management in urban environments.*

Keywords: AI; waste management; robotics; sustainability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of plastic and aluminium products have been ubiquitous in our daily lives. Their inert nature and cheap cost for mass production has led to these materials being widely used in many food and beverage products in the form of wrappings and containers. However, with growing human populations, so does the consumption of these materials. Thus, the management of the aluminium and plastic waste becoming increasingly important and challenging. In developing countries, importing this rubbish has been a source of income (Amondi, 2025). However, these counties often lack an adequate waste management and disposal facilities, leading to dangerous chemicals seeping into the soil, water and air (Lama, 2025).

Despite the waste sorting awareness being promoted globally to facilitate the process of waste management and recycling, the enforcement is dependent on countries, with developing countries

mostly lacks (Lama, 2025). This leads to the aluminium and plastic waste being mixed together with other forms of wastes, oftentimes organic. Therefore, one of the most prevalent issues of plastic and aluminium waste management is an effective means of discerning plastic and aluminium waste from other wastes.

The advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) can potentially accelerate the developmental progress of waste sorting. Currently AI image recognition is able to extract relevant information from images, and real time video, which has produce cutting edge technologies including autonomous vehicles, security scan in airports and content media moderation (Khedlekar, 2025). The YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a real-time object detection Ai model widely used for robotics, driverless cars, security scanning, and traffic monitoring applications. (Juan Terven et al., 2023). It produced a high accuracy, speed and reliability This YOLO image recognition power could be harnessed to recognise plastic and aluminium based waste and thus enabling incorporation of AI technology to perform waste sorting with greater efficiency than humans.

This study aims to design, build and evaluate an integrated YOLO AI based system to classify and sort plastics and cans which we called Sortify. Through assessment of Sortify, we can evaluate its potential ability to be adapted in waste management facilities in developing countries, such as in Malaysia.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Sortify System

Sortify consisted of a conveyor belt, a robot arm, cameras and sensors cameras (Figure 1). The YOLO11 (Ultralytics, USA) AI model was used for image recognition. We downloaded, installed and running the software and performing following the official documentation (<https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/yolo11/>).

Figure 1. Sortify Prototype

2.2 Sortify Efficiency Assessment

We tested Sortify with various forms of plastic and aluminium wastes. The efficiency of the Sortify was assessed based on time taken for the YOLO AI to detect the object, followed by recognising the object and placing the object into correct 'plastic' or 'aluminium' bin. Then we assessed the accuracy

of object detection by confidence scoring. The experiment run was performed twice. The demonstration of the prototype is available online https://youtu.be/eUQUqJIN1Q4?si=Q8EYKA10y9dkwc_0.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Sortify Image Processing Time

The time taken for detecting forms or aluminium wastes was an average of 2.8 seconds longer than plastics (Table 1). Similarly, it was longer for Sortify to categorise the waste into the correct bin, with aluminium waste taking 2.4 seconds longer than plastics.

Table 1. Sortify aluminium and plastic waste processing time

Materials	Aluminium	Plastic
Average time taken to detect (s)	13.3	10.5
Average time taken to recognise (s)	11.0	8.6

3.2 Sortify Accuracy

The aluminium confidence confidence in the first trial was 93%, and it increased to 97% in the second trial. In comparison, plastics showed a decrease in accuracy, with the first trial showing a confidence of 88% and the second trial improving to 95%.

Table 2 Accuracy of Sortify object detection

Waste type	Confidence in first trial (%)	Confidence in second trial (%)
Aluminium	93	97
Plastic	88	95

4. DISCUSSION

Artificial intelligence (AI) and IoT-enabled approaches can empower cities to manage the waste collection. This work proposes an intelligent approach to route recommendation in an IoT-enabled waste management system given spatial constraints. From the moment an object stops on the conveyor belt to the point the robotic arm places it into the correct container, the entire detection and sorting process takes approximately 5 seconds per action. The developed system demonstrates accurate data ranging from 88% to 97%.

Overall, the system performed efficiently, though further optimization is possible in object detection particularly for aluminium waste. It is possible the lack of aluminium waste colour variety in the YOLO11 AI training datasets contribute to the detection and recognition latency (Ali & Zhang, 2024). It is possible that using different YOLO variants, such as the more recent EcoDetect-YOLO which has demonstrated increased capabilities small-object detection, could further enhance Sortify capability (Liu et al., 2024).

5. CONCLUSION

Our study shows that AI, Robotics and IoT system can be effectively applied in environment to improve human living standard. This system is also tested and confirm to be fully compatible with Android, iOS and Windows. Overall, the system is currently at technology readiness level (TRL) 6, which means the prototype has been demonstrated in a relevant environment, and fulfils the United Nations' Sustainability Development Goals (SDG); SDG 9 (industry, innovation and infrastructure) and SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities). This shows that the system not only functions as intended but is also ready to progress to a more advanced development stage, potentially moving towards commercialization or field deployment. These findings support the potential of our product to be implemented nationwide for efficient waste management.

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